

PSYCHOLOGICAL MECHANISMS OF FORMING A REFLECTIVE CULTURE

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Abstract. The article substantiates the role of self-analysis, metacognitive processes, motivation, empathy and professional identification as psychological mechanisms in the formation of a reflexive culture. It also highlights the pedagogical and psychological conditions, training and interactive methods that serve to develop reflexive activity. The results of the study allow us to develop methodological recommendations aimed at developing a reflexive culture in the process of training future specialists, in particular psychologists.

Keywords: reflection, reflexive culture, psychological mechanisms, self-analysis, metacognition, professional development.

In modern society, the professional activity of a psychologist is directly related not only to theoretical knowledge and practical skills, but also to the level of personal maturity, self-awareness and professional reflection. In this regard, the issue of forming a reflexive culture in future psychologists is emerging as one of the urgent tasks of the higher education system. A reflexive culture represents a person's ability to consciously analyze and evaluate his own activities, mental state, values and professional behavior.

Globalization, the rapid development of digital technologies, and complex situations arising in professional activities require specialists to have a high level of flexibility, critical thinking, and self-management skills. This requires a deep development of the reflection process, that is, the formation of a reflexive culture. In psychological research, reflection is recognized as an important factor in understanding the inner world of a person, reconsidering professional experience, and self-development. [2]

At the same time, the analysis of scientific sources shows that, although the issue of the formation of a reflexive culture has been partially covered in many studies, insufficient attention has been paid to the systematic study of its psychological mechanisms. In particular, the influence of self-analysis, metacognitive processes, motivation, empathy, and professional identification on the development of a reflexive culture requires in-depth scientific substantiation.

The purpose of this article is to theoretically analyze the main psychological

mechanisms of the formation of a reflexive culture and determine their significance in the professional training of future psychologists. The results of the study will serve to develop effective pedagogical and psychological approaches aimed at developing a reflexive culture in the process of higher education. [3]

In modern psychological research, the concept of reflection has attracted the attention of many researchers. In modern and classical literature, many explanations and concepts are given regarding the term “reflection”. In scientific sources, the concept of reflection is interpreted as follows. Reflexive abilities include: It means self-awareness and evaluation, as well as analysis of one’s strengths and weaknesses. The following definitions are given to the concept of reflection: “Reflection” (Latin *reflexio* – “looking back”) was originally formed in philosophy and is the process of observing what is happening in a person’s own mind”. In other words, “it is an activity of self-knowledge aimed at revealing the essence of a person’s spiritual world” [9].

Reflection is the process of self-awareness through which a person analyzes, understands and evaluates his own thoughts and activities. Reflective culture, on the other hand, refers to the culture of carrying out this process in a conscious, systematic and socially acceptable manner. The specificity of the profession of a psychologist is that a representative of this field must be able to deeply understand his own feelings and reactions in the process of working with the psyche of others, manage them and strive for constant self-development. Therefore, the formation of a reflexive culture in the process of psychological education should become an integral part of the educational process [1].

This study is conducted to identify the psychological characteristics of the formation of a reflexive culture in future psychologists, analyze the factors affecting this process, and develop effective methods for its formation. The relevance of the topic is closely related to the needs of modern education and society, and directly affects the quality of psychological services, professional development and personal stability of specialists.

The purpose of the study is to identify the psychological characteristics of the formation of a reflexive culture in future psychologists, analyze the factors influencing their development, and develop methodological foundations for the effective organization of this process.

Objectives of the study:

1. Study the theoretical foundations of the concepts of reflection and reflexive culture;
2. To determine the place of reflexive culture in the development of the personality of a future psychologist;

3. Identify psychological factors that influence the formation of a reflective culture;
4. Selection and application of diagnostic methods that determine the level of reflexive culture in future psychologists;
5. Recommend effective psychological training technologies aimed at developing a reflective culture;
6. Develop practical recommendations based on the results obtained.

Research object: The process of professional development of future psychologists (students) studying psychology.

The following methods were used in the study: questionnaire, tests, observation, and interview.

Based on the results of the research, training programs, recommendations, and methodological guidelines aimed at developing a reflexive culture for students studying psychology can be developed. This will serve to increase the level of professional training of future psychologists.

The formation of a reflexive culture in the training of future psychologists is one of the main factors contributing to their professional growth, socio-psychological adaptation and personal stability. By developing this culture in the educational process, students acquire skills such as self-awareness, self-assessment, analysis of activity results, and establishing proper relationships with colleagues and clients.

However, current observations show that reflective culture is not sufficiently formed among students studying psychology, and methodological work aimed at their development in most cases consists of general approaches. Also, the inextricable link of reflective culture with factors such as individual psychological characteristics, personal motivation, emotional intelligence, and professional interest has not been sufficiently studied. Therefore, it is important to deeply analyze the psychological characteristics of the formation of reflective culture in future psychologists, and to develop effective methods and technologies in this regard.

This study aims to address these issues, to study the theoretical foundations of the process of forming a reflexive culture in future psychologists, to identify its psychological characteristics and to recommend ways of its effective development. The relevance of this topic is of immense importance not only in improving the quality of psychological education, but also in ensuring the effectiveness of the activities of practicing psychologists in the future.

Reflection is the ability of a person to analyze, evaluate, and improve their own activities, thoughts, and feelings. For future psychologists, this skill is a central component of professional competence. Reflective culture, on the other hand, means

conducting this process on a conscious, systematic, and cultural level.

Today, psychologists need to be not only specialists who help others, but also individuals who can develop their own personal qualities and regularly analyze their own activities. Therefore, the formation of a reflexive culture increases their professional maturity.

A reflective culture is self-analysis, willingness to change, regular self-evaluation, and creative and constructive thinking.

Psychologists who lack a reflective culture are at risk of burnout, emotional distress, or poor judgment. Reflection is an important tool in identifying and addressing these risks [5].

For students studying psychology, a reflective approach develops their level of mastery, independent thinking, and creativity. This is an important factor in improving the quality and effectiveness of education.

The demand for psychological services in society is increasing. This creates a need to improve the quality of services and the skills of specialists. A reflexive culture is an important component that meets these needs.

In studying the topic of psychological features of the formation of a reflexive culture in future psychologists, several prominent psychologists and their works play an important role. In particular, Donald Schon developed his concept of "reflexive practice". He called on psychologists and other professionals to analyze their activities and adapt to changes. This is especially important for increasing the effectiveness of psychological care. [7]

Psychologist David Kolb made significant contributions to the study of the reflective process through his experiential learning model. He believed that learning is an activity-based process, which helps psychologists analyze their own experiences. [6]

The relationship between learning and thinking is central to the work of John Dewey, who saw the process of reflection as a fundamental tool for the proper analysis of thoughts and the solution of problems. [5]

Lev Vygotsky analyzed the relationship between psychological development and reflective processes. He focused on the development of self-analysis and thinking. [3]

In short, reflexive culture is the ability to consciously apply psychological knowledge in practice, to analyze one's own activities, and to develop self-evaluation skills. For future psychologists, this culture is an integral part of professional maturity.

Psychologically, reflection is a process of internal reflection, awareness of emotions, and evaluation of one's own actions, which has a positive impact on the

conscious development of the individual. [6]

Research shows that by developing a reflective culture, future psychologists in their professional activities:

- can deeply analyze problem situations;
- can engage in empathetic communication with the client;
- will be independent and responsible in decision-making;
- ensures regular growth in its activities.

The use of curricula, practical exercises, and interactive methods (trainings, role-playing games) plays an important role in the formation of a reflective culture.

Here are some recommendations for developing a reflective culture:

It is necessary to increase the number of tasks that develop reflection in the educational process (essays, diary writing, case analysis), and to activate personal and professional reflection through psychological training.

During the internship, it is necessary to develop special formats for student psychologists to analyze their work in writing and orally, and to organize reflexive discussions based on feedback with mentors.

In personal development, it is advisable to regularly keep a reflective diary for self-analysis, as well as use self-awareness and management training and meditation techniques.

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